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Review Article

A STUDY AND REVIEW OF CENTELLA ASIATICA**Kodhai.V**

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1. Abstract:

Centella asiatica, popularly referred to as Gotu kola, is an herb with medicinal qualities that has been utilised for centuries in many different civilisations. This perennial plant, which is mostly found in Asia, has long been a mainstay of Southeast Asian, Chinese, and Ayurvedic medicine. The plant is well known for its many health advantages, especially in the management of skin disorders, improvement of cognitive function, and healing of wounds. The pharmacological properties of *Centella asiatica* are mostly attributed to its bioactive constituents, including asiaticoside, madecassoside, and asiatic acid. It is well known that these triterpenoids encourage the manufacture of collagen, which is necessary to preserve the flexibility and integrity of the skin. As a result, *Centella asiatica* is frequently utilised in cosmetic formulas for scar therapy, anti-aging, and enhancing skin moisture. Additionally, *Centella asiatica* demonstrates neuroprotective qualities, which makes its function in treating long-term illnesses including venous insufficiency and repairing wounds. Even though it's widely used, research is still being done to better understand the mechanisms underlying these effects and determine standard dosages for therapeutic use. All things considered, *Centella asiatica* is still a useful natural medication with a wide range of uses in both conventional and alternative medicine.

Keywords: *Centella asiatica*, improve memory, triterpenoids, anti-aging, wound healing.

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2. INTRODUCTION:

Plants have been an important source of medicine for thousands of years. Even today, the world Health Organization (WHO) estimates that up to 80% of people still primarily on traditional remedies such as herbs for their medicines. The medicinal value of these plants is due to the presence of a variety of phytochemicals and their elemental composition. The drugs derived from the major component of traditional medicine like Ayurveda and Sidda. The investigation of herbal substances was conducted due to their efficient medicinal value, which laid the platform for the discovery of newer medicines to cure ailments. One of the important plants with its great medicinal value is *Centella asiatica* leaves which belongs to the Family Apiaceae.

Centella asiatica:

Fig no: 1 Centella asiatica

- ❖ *Centella asiatica* is a genus of 53 species of flowering plants in the subfamily Mackinlayoideae. The genus is sometimes placed in family Araliaceae; however, recent studies utilising molecular data place *Centella* within Apiaceae. *Centella asiatica* also known as Gotu Kola (or) *Centella asiatica*, is an herbaceous plant native to southeast Asia.

3. TAXONOMY OF CENTELLA ASIATICA ⁽²⁾

Classification	Name
Kingdom	Eukaryota\Plantae
Subkingdom	Embryophyta
Division	Spermatophyta
Subdivision	Angiospermae
Class	Dicotyledoneae
Subclass	Rosidae
Superorder	Aralianae
Order	Apiales\Umbelliflorae
Family	Apiaceae\Umbelliferae
Subfamily	Mackinlayoideae\Hydrocotyle
Genus	Centella
Species	Asiatica

- ❖ Its commonly used in traditional medicine and has a long history of use in Ayurvedic and traditional Chinese medicine. It is believed to have various health benefits, including improving cognition, reduce anxiety and promoting wound healing.
- ❖ Urban *Centella asiatica* (Linn) is a member of the Umbelliferae\ Apiaceae family. For countries Malaysia and other Asian countries have utilised their compounds as a traditional herbal remedy ⁽¹⁾.
- ❖ This herb has long been used as an antibacterial, immunostimulant, wound healer, treatment for inflammatory skin disorders psoriasis and eczema. According to earlier research, the presence of pentacyclic triterpene acids (madecarsic acid) and their glycosides (asiaticoside and madecassoside).
- ❖ Almost all phytochemical research focused on leaves. This perennial medicinal herb is commonly found in tropical and subtropical regions, including India, Srilanka and Bangladesh ⁽⁵⁾.
- ❖ *Centella asiatica* includes several triterpenes and saponins, including asiaticoside, Asiatic acid, sapogenins, madecassic acid, vellarin, adecassoside, glycosides and Centelloside.
- ❖ In India, it grows to a height of 600-1800 metres above sea level on moist, clayey (or) sandy soils, making a thick green carpet. *Centella asiatica* has a glabrous stem and long petiolated fleshy leaves that root at the nodes.
- ❖ It is a delicately fragrant shrub that can grow up to 15cm tall. The stem is smooth, and roots occurs at the nodes. It grows profusely in damp, swampy, and wet areas, blossoming from April to June with white, purple (or) pink flowers.

4.VERNACULAR NAMES OF CENTELLA ASIATICA⁽⁶⁾

Regional Language	Vernacular Name
China	Fo-ti-tieng, Chi-hsueuh-ts'ao
USA Pennywort	Indian Pennywort, Marsh
Hawaii	Pohe Kula
Nepal	Ghodtapre
Urdu	Brahmi
Malay	Pegaga
Malayalam	Kodagam
Hindi	Mandookaparni
Bengali	Thankuni

5.MORPHOLOGY OF CENTELLA ASIATICA

1.Stems:

Straited, glabrous, rooting at the nodes. Flourishes extensively in shady, damp, marshy and wet places such as paddy fields and riverbanks forming a dense green carpet and rather than clayey soil, the sandy loam (60% sand) is found to be most fertile soil for its generation⁽³⁾.

Fig no: 2 Stems of Centella asiatica

2. Seeds:

Pendulous embryos which are laterally compressed⁽⁴⁾.

Fig no: 3 Seeds of Centella asiatica

3. Leaves:

2-6 cm long and 1.5-5 cm wide, 1-3 from each node of stems, orbicular-remform⁽⁵⁾.

Fig no: 4 Leaves of Centella asiatica

4. Flowers:

Fascicled umbels each umbel consisting of 3-4 white to purple (or) pink flowers, flowering occur in the month of April-June⁽⁶⁾.

Fig no: 5 Flower of Centella asiatica

5. Fruits:

Borne throughout the growing season in approx. 2 inches long, globular in shape and strongly thickened pericarp⁽²⁾.

The small and compressed contained 7 to 9 ridged and have sized of 8mm long.

Fig no: 6 Fruit of *Centella asiatica*

A). MICROLOGICAL STUDIES OF *CENTELLA ASIATICA*

Microscopic studies of *Centella asiatica* involve examining its anatomy of its leaves, stems, and roots at a microscopic level. These studies typically focus on features like,

1. Leaf anatomy:

The leaves of *Centella asiatica* are known for their characteristic structure. Under the microscope, you can observe the epidermis, mesophyll, and vascular tissues. The epidermal cells may have trichomes (hair like structures), and the stomata (pores for gas exchange) can be studied.

2. Stem anatomy:

Microscopic examination of the stem reveals the arrangement of vascular bundles, the presence of xylem and phloem, and other supportive tissues. The stem's structure helps in understanding the plant's growth and nutrient transport.

3. Root anatomy:

The root structure can be studied to observe the root hair cells, cortex, endodermis, and vascular cylinder. These studies can provide insights into how the plant absorbs water and nutrients.

B). MACROLOGICAL STUDIES OF *CENTELLA ASIATICA*

Macrological studies involve examining the plant's observable characteristics without the aid of a microscope.

1. Leaves:

Shape: The leaves of *Centella asiatica* are typically round to reniform (kidney shaped) with a slightly lobed margin. The leaves are attached to long petioles.

Color: The leaves are usually bright green.

Texture: The laves have a smooth texture, and they are often thin and delicate.

2. Stem:

Structure: The stems are slender, creeping, and greenish in colour. They are stoloniferous, meaning they can produce roots and new shoots at the nodes, allowing the plant to spread horizontally.

Surface: The stem surface is generally smooth and may have a slightly reddish tinge.

3. Flowers:

Appearance: The flowers are small, white to pinkish, and arranged in clusters (umbels). Each cluster contains 3 to 4 flowers.

Structure: Each flower has five petals, and the flowers are Horne close to the ground or near the leaf nodes.

4. Roots:

Type: The roots are fibrous and are primarily found at the nodes where the stem touches the ground.

Function: The roots help anchor the plant and absorb nutrients from the soil.

5. Fruit:

Appearance: The fruit of *Centella asiatica* is a small, flattened, and oval shaped schizocarp. It contains two seeds and typically has a rough surface.

6.CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF *CENTELLA ASIATICA*

1. Triterpenoids:**A) Asiaticoside:**

Promotes wound healing by stimulating collagen and synthesis and enhancing antioxidant activity. It also exhibits anti-inflammatory properties.

Fig no: 7 Structure of Asiaticoside

B) Asiatic acid:

Enhances collagen formation and is effective against inflammation.

Fig no: 8 Structure of Asiatic acid

C) Madecassoside:

Similar to asiaticoside, it aids in wound healing and has anti-inflammatory effects.

Fig no: 9 Structure of Madecassoside

D) Madecassic acid:

Supports wound healing, collagen production and has anti-inflammatory properties.

Fig no: 10 Structure of Madecassic acid

2.Flavonoids:**A) Quercetin:**

Acts as an antioxidant and anti-inflammatory agent, contributing to skin health and immune function.

B) Kaempferol:

Offers antioxidant protection and potential anti-cancer effects.

C) Rutin:

Supports vascular health and has antioxidant properties.

D) Phytosterols:

These compounds recontribute to *Centella asiatica*'s anti-inflammatory effects and may help reduce cholesterol levels.

E) Amino acids:

Essential for protein synthesis and various metabolic processes, supporting overall health and skin regeneration.

7. MINERALS AND VITAMINS OF CENTELLA ASIATICA

Centella asiatica contains minerals like calcium, potassium, magnesium as well as vitamin C which contribute to its antioxidant and skin health benefits.

1. Minerals:**A) Calcium:**

Essential for bone health and muscle function.

B) Potassium:

Important for nerve function, muscle control, blood pressure regulation.

C) Magnesium:

Supports muscle and nerve function immune system health and bone strength.

2. VITAMINS:**A) Vitamin C:**

Known for its antioxidant properties, which help protect cells from damage and contribute to collagen synthesis, important for skin health and wound healing.

B) Vitamin B complex ⁽⁸⁾:

It includes vitamin such as B₁ (thiamine), B₂ (riboflavin), B₃ (niacin), B₅ (carotene), B₆ (pyridoxine), B₉ (folate).

8. PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF CENTELLA ASIATICA**1. Memory Enhancing Activiyy ⁽⁹⁾:**

The preliminary screening results suggested that oral administration of *Centella asiatica* for fifteen days improved learning and memory in three months old mice, as measured by the radial arm maze test. The radial arm maze is a common method for testing spatial memory.

2. Anti-bacterial activity:

Asiaticoside can effectively treat *Bacillus leprae*, *Mycobacterium TB* and *Entamoeba histolytic*. Methanolic extract of *Centella asiatica* inhibited *V. alginolitus*, *V. vulnificus*, and *Streptococcus* ⁽¹⁰⁾.

The methanolic extract of *Centella asiatica* shown antibacterial activity against three vibrio species (*v. harveyi*, *v. alginoliticus* and *v. parahaemoliticus*) but not acetone, chloroform (or) hexane extracts ⁽¹¹⁾.

3. Anti diabetic:

Centella asiatica's triterpenic fraction improves microcirculation and reduces capillary permeability making it beneficial for diabetic microangiopathy. *Centella asiatica* contains a triterpenic component that helps prevent degradation ⁽¹²⁾.

Methanolic and Ethanolic extracts significantly reduced blood glucose levels to normal levels in a tolerance test ⁽²¹⁾.

4. Anti-oxidant activity:

A study found that asiaticoside dramatically enhanced the amounts of catalase, superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase, ascorbic acid, and vitamin E in rats ⁽¹⁴⁾.

5. Anti-tumour activity:

Centella asiatica's methanol extract inhibits tumour cell proliferation without harming lymphocytes whereas its aqueous extract protects against colon carcinogenesis ⁽¹⁵⁾.

6. Skin protective activity:

Skin aging becomes noticeable due to decrease in the levels of type1 collagen. Asiaticoside isolated from *C. asiatica* showed synthesis of type1 collagen in human dermal fibroblast cells ⁽¹⁵⁾.

7. Central nervous system:

Asiaticoside derivatives decrease (or) prevent H2O2 induced cell death, lower intracellular free radical levels, and protect against beta amyloid neurotoxicity. *C. asiatica* extract has been shown to the boost brain GABA levels ⁽¹⁶⁾.

8. Cardiovascular:

C. asiatica extracts effectively treat ankle, venous insufficiency, foot swelling, edema, and improve capillary filtration rate and microcirculatory parameters. In rats, an alcoholic extract of the entire plant demonstrated cardioprotective efficacy against ischemia-reperfusion myocardial infraction ⁽¹⁷⁾.

9. Neuroprotective effect:

C. asiatica extract can prevent monosodium glutamate-induced neurodegeneration, *C. asiatica* water extract protects the brain of prepubertal mice from oxidant caused by 3-nitropropionic acid. It increased glutathione levels and antioxidant defences in brain areas ⁽¹⁸⁾.

10. Wound healing property:

C. asiatica increase in DNA, protein, and collagen content of granulation tissues was observed on supplementation of extract of *C. asiatica* resulting in collagen synthesis and cellular proliferation at wound site ⁽¹⁹⁾.

9.vbnPHARMACOKINETICS OF CENTELLA ASIATICA:

Grimaldi determined the pharmacokinetics of asiatica acid following oral administration of the complete triterpenic fraction of *C. asiatica*. Repeated oral administration of total triterpenic fraction daily for 7 days results in significantly higher t_{1/2} and AUC₀₋₂₄ compared to single oral administration, indicating accumulation of Asiatic acid during chronic treatment. This is well correlated with the in vivo transformation of asiaticoside to Asiatic acid.

10. CONCLUSION:

Centella asiatica, a key component of traditional medical systems such as Ayurveda and Traditional Chinese medical, has shown great promise as a therapeutic agent in contemporary medicine. Its many pharmacological actions, which include neuroprotective, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, wound-healing, and cognitive-enhancing benefits, demonstrate its usefulness as a therapeutic plant. Bioactive chemicals, notably triterpenoids such as asiaticoside, contribute significantly to these effects and hold promise for the treatment of neurological illnesses, skin ailments, and cardiovascular diseases. Current study has confirmed *Centella asiatica*'s ability to improve cognitive function, reduce anxiety, and promote skin health, making it a viable candidate for treating age-related cognitive decline and anxiety disorders. Furthermore, its wound-healing qualities have been found to speed up tissue repair and promote scar formation, which is particularly useful in dermatology and surgery. Despite its promising effects, *Centella asiatica*'s entire medicinal potential has yet to be explored. Most investigations to date have been preclinical, with few human clinical trials to corroborate these findings. Standardisation of extracts, determination of optimal doses, and a better understanding of their pharmacokinetics and long-term safety are critical for their incorporation into standard medical practice. Furthermore, the intricacy of its bioactive elements suggests that the plant may

function synergistically, necessitating detailed research on its overall effects rather than separate substances. Exploring its molecular mechanisms of action could lead to new drug development opportunities, particularly for illnesses with few therapy alternatives. In conclusion, *Centella asiatica* shows significant promise as a natural medicinal agent with numerous applications. However, more rigorous study is required to fully realise its promise and convert conventional applications into scientifically proven medicines.

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